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Main contribution:

Broadcasting of digital shows

Title of paper abstract to be submitted: **Broadcasting Digitally Generated Gameshows**

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Broadcasting Digitally Generated Gameshows

Historical Background

Game shows are historically among the first entertainment shows to be broadcasted by television.

What does "digital play" mean in the framework of the Amusement project? The answer, that comes at the end of a long historical evolution of the entertainment culture, is simple. Bring the best of the past (mostly the possibility of interaction among spectators and between spectators and actors) along with the best of modern technology (namely the possibility of interaction at distance).

Normally, in a game show, there are three types of fundamental roles: a host, the players and the audience. The audience can be divided in turn into two groups: the in-site audience and the at-home audience. This was an "escamotage", implemented since the beginning of the TV era, meant to provide the show with both an interactive audience in the studio that could applaud and react as well as a vast audience that could be located anywhere TV screens were found.

Now it is worth noticing that the crowd sitting in even the world's biggest stadium is, in order of magnitude, smaller than an average TV audience. The trade-off was thus to have two types of audience: one interactive (though small in size) and one larger (though completely passive). Yet today it is possible to have an audience that is simultaneously both large and interactive.

In the digital age we have another advantage that has been somehow overlooked. Today it is possible not only to convert an analog image of a show into a digital stream of bits, as today's digital TV normally does (the relevant information is, strictly technically speaking, digital, of course, but, logically, the information is organized, simply, as an "analog" of the real play, since they do nothing more than replicate the image of the real play), but also to create, as we do in the Amusement project, a digital show directly from scratch using digital actors.

Implementation and Rationale for the Broadcasting of a Networked Game

The Amusement Center has been implemented with a distributed client server architecture. The architecture is truly distributed in the sense that all the different functionalities of the server can be (and, in fact, are) distributed on different computers, that can be addressed by different IPs, and can be (and are) physically distributed at different geographic locations.

In the Amusement Project, the Amusement Center Server (to be referred to simply as the Server) is at the most abstract level a system with these basic functions:

1. To gather information from all users (function mode: many to one).
2. To relay to all users the information generated by all the other users (function mode: many to many).

In the Amusement Project the Amusement Center Client (to be referred to simply as the Client) is at the most abstract level possible a system with these basic functions:

1. To transmit the locally generated information to the Server (functionality mode: one to one).
2. To receive from the Server information generated from all the other users (functionality mode: one to one).
3. To "render" the information in graphic, acoustic, and textual modes.

Our View on Virtuality

The *Client* hardware has the function of rendering the information received. This information constitutes, for the user, not only a sort of "window" into the Amusement Center, but, more specifically, what we can define here as an embodiment/disembodiment tool. In other words, not only can the user "see" by means of his/her Client what happens in the Amusement Center, and modify (by means of pointing devices and keyboard commands) the "world" of the Amusement Center, but he feels and behaves as if he were physically there. It is important to notice that **the presence of the user does not have to be an exact replica of his or her physical presence "on the other side of the screen"**.

In our view, the virtual presence can actually capitalize on the **differences** that exist between the *real* world and the *virtual* one and not be limited by them. We should bear in mind that one of the most fundamental goals of the Amusement Project is to bring the best interaction possible to people that, for any reason, happen to be distant in space. In the Amusement Project we don't seek to simulate the real world nor to build the best possible replica of it. The philosophical background of this concept is related to the fact that human beings have a great capacity to interact using symbols. Sometimes those symbols are very abstract, as in the case of textual and verbal communication, but sometimes as in some "visual arts" they may have a defined physical shape. Of course the symbolism of those shapes is sometimes only loosely coupled with the physical shape, and this coupling depends on many factors.

The first lesson learned then is that the virtual environment need not be a perfect replica of the real world. Moreover, we started with an approach that put the fundamental psychological and social needs of human beings at a premium. In other words, we tried to look first at needs and only then to develop a response to those needs. For example: one fundamental need is for people to get in touch with one another. The technology used to do it is of secondary importance. This has been confirmed by our user and expert surveys. Paradoxically, for many people e-mail is still sufficient to communicate; it works consistently and we trust it through experience. Taking cues from this sort of simple lesson, we got rid of the hype surrounding much new technology and virtual reality, and we carefully studied what people need to interact at a distance. Surprisingly enough, the exact positioning of objects appears not to be truly important for most purposes, as demonstrated, for example, by the commercial fiasco of "data gloves".

In analyzing the degree of "reality" of a virtual world we shouldn't forget that there is an "induced" effect. The Russian scientist Pavlov consistently fed his dogs after ringing a bell, leading them to

associate the spur of food with the sound of a bell; then, when hearing only the bell, the dogs salivated. The same phenomenon occurs with us. Thus we are in a position to associate as a conditioned reflex a spur, such as a whisper in an ear, with the sensation of a breath in the neck, even when only the acoustic stimulus (easily reproducible electronically) is present, and a real breath on the neck is absent.

Now "virtual reality" has added the interactive dimension to a phenomenon that already existed and that was called "cinema" or "theater". Cinema and theater evoked by means of stimuli that are technically easier to reproduce (sight and hearing) the other complex of phenomena that are associated to them through pavlovian conditioned reflexes. It must also be said that the virtual dimension in the view of some psychologists as John Suler of Ryder University has always existed, and can be identified with the oniric dimension. This view is not shared by most of the scientists interviewed in our expert survey on the ground that "when dreaming we are unconscious".

Therefore, on the basis of what is discussed above, we will limit our use of devices to either the classic but ever-functional pointing device called the mouse, and to new devices that "non-invasively" transduce the position of the whole body to the position of the user's avatar. (This means that also the user's avatar view changes accordingly.)

For example, if a person moves inside a confined space like a room, the other users see the person's avatar moving accordingly and the person moving sees his/her point of view on the screen changing accordingly. (This is more effective if the screen is not a computer screen but a projected image on a big panel behind onto which a projector is pointed.)

The necessary level of realism in moving is obtained by triggering the predefined gesture "walking". We have observed that the other users would not notice the difference between a predefined walking gesture and a gesture made on the basis of a detailed capture of the real walking pattern of the person. Indeed we have been experimenting in the Amusement Project not only with "walking" gestures, but also with any other gestures that the user/person may want to "transmit" to the other users.

Thus, the basic principle investigated is that there is the possibility to transduce and transmit only the position of the "center of mass" of the body in order to communicate the displacement of an avatar with almost the same effect as transmitting all the coordinates and rotations of all the single body segments. After all, the latter would be a very "analogue" approach, and we in the Amusement Project are studying the possibilities of digital media.

In this way digital transmission of digitally-generated shows becomes possible. The two closing figures illustrate the gains in terms of bandwidth and associated costs.

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